

Where is My FAIRLab¹?
The Loneliness of the Long-Distance Researcher²

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As a senior scholar of literature and an expert in early twentieth-century Spanish literature, I have had to confront theoretical, critical, methodological, and technical challenges to adapt my object of study —texts and con/texts— to the demands of changing times. Two cross-cutting axes have radically unsettled my knowledge, transforming it and reconfiguring it into a historically grounded present: feminism and digitalisation. Drawing on national, regional, and university archives and libraries, I have gradually enriched my own personal Library of Babel, first with books, articles, and photocopies, and later with DVDs, PDFs, e-books, and links to multiple delocalised resources that came to occupy the shelves of my library or the folders of my personal computer. Messy spaces! or rather, ecosystems ordered from within the dystopia of expert knowledge.

And now what? A world saturated with acronyms, overlapping and entangled with dispersed contents: GLAM, FAIR, CLARIN-ERIC, DARIAH, CLARIAH-ES, CLARIAH-CM, SSHOMP, GoTriple, ECHOES, EOSC... Open Science, LLMs, Artificial Intelligence, internationalisation, standards, community... My avatar moves through it in solitude, searching for —and finding— materials in HathiTrust, Europeana, Hispana, Biblioteca Nacional, Biblioteca Virgual Miguel de Cervantes, , and my beloved [Biblioteca Digital Mnemosine](#), devoted to rare and forgotten texts and authors from the so-called Silver Age of Spanish literature.

And now, more! From the CLARIAH-CM Node, we aim to contribute to CLARIN's PressMint Flagship with two resources: (1) [Patrimonio Digital Complutense](#) (PDC), which disseminates in digital format a significant portion of its heritage holdings, with the aim of sharing and highlighting a digitised documentary heritage (ninth to twentieth centuries); and (2) the [Digital Library of the Community of Madrid](#) (BDCM), which offers a rich collection of unique works that constitute Madrid's bibliographic heritage, together with its Digital Newspaper Archive.

What can a long-distance researcher do with all of this? There are two possible ways of approaching:

1.- From the anger and rebelliousness of someone who cannot encompass everything (for lack of time and unfamiliarity) and who finds that the desired content is only weakly aligned with international Open Science

¹ Paraphrasing the musical *My Fair Lady*, based on George Bernard Shaw's play *Pygmalion*.

² Paraphrasing Alan Sillitoe's *The Loneliness of the Long-Distance Runner*.

³ The interplay between personal reflection and literary works is more apparent in the English version of this essay.

and FAIR data policies: large-scale downloads and APIs; OCR that can be assessed and exported; advanced full-text search; interoperable metadata with persistent identifiers; and formats/standards (IIIF, ALTO, METS/MODS) that make it possible to build reproducible, reusable corpora. Content, data, resources, and services in Spanish are still lacking.

2.- From the stance of pragmatic acceptance adopted by those who seek to align efforts among experts and institutions at the European level, as in the case of the [European Cloud for Heritage Open Science](#) (ECHOES), which fosters access to data, scientific resources, training workshops, and tools, and [the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage](#) —linked to Europeana— whose purpose is to accelerate the transformation of the cultural heritage sector. Likewise, the [Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace](#) (SSHOMP) repository of CLARIN and DARIAH provides information aligned with corpora, workflows, data, services, and tools.

But where is My FAIRLab? It still must be built, and there are two possible routes for doing so:

1.- The cooperative creation of platforms/laboratories for the integration of resources and tools. One example is [Chronopress](#), built on a corpus of approximately 100,000 carefully selected press excerpts (1945–1964), linguistically analysed at the morphosyntactic level and tagged to provide outputs in the form of time series, concordances, maps, word profiles, and usage scenarios. Another example is [Spyral Notebook](#), an advanced development of the well-known Voyant Tools. Spyral is a notebook environment that brings together writing, code, and data in the service of reading, analysing, and interpreting digital texts.

2.- Building MyFAIRLab — A Lab of One's Own⁴ (Spanish literature, 1868–1939; feminism; and digitisation)— in which, through an expert AI, I could search for my corpora, my data, my tools and services; enrich them; analyse them; and make them interoperable and reproducible without needing to install any software. **MyFAIRLab** would be a dream for many long-distance researchers who possess rich, well-grounded expert knowledge but limited familiarity with digital tools —tools that, moreover, they find increasingly obsolete from one day to the next.

The major shift we are witnessing is an integral transformation of the reading process (and of knowledge production): from analogue to digital, from the near to the distant. Libraries will remain meaningful insofar as they occupy that **intermediate space** between global standards and user-proximate localisation.

⁴ Paraphrasing Virginia Woolf in *A Room of One's Own*.